

PSYCHODIAGNOSTICS OF MEMORY DISORDERS

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Abstract: The article focuses on the methods of psychodiagnostics methods used in the diagnosis of disorders of cognitive processes, especially memory disorders, and their necessity and importance, and is devoted to the analysis of empirical research on the features of their application in the field of medicine.

Key words: cognitive functions, cognitive disorders, medical psychodiagnostics, psychoneurological diseases, clinical psychometrics, methodology, memory.

The relevance. In clinical practice, people who have complained of cognitive disorders have shown conditions related to forgetfulness, difficulty concentrating, decreased mental ability, and increased fatigue during intellectual work. Diagnosis of its symptoms is primary in the treatment of patients with cognitive disorders. Based on this, the main goal of this article is to focus on the methods used in the process of psychological diagnosis of such disorders and their significance. One group of methods used for the diagnosis of disorders in cognitive functions is designed to study the characteristics of memory.

Methodology of the research problem. A.R. Luria's "Memorization of 10 words" test, "Numbers recall" test, "Visual memory" test, and "Benton's visual retention" test are mentioned in the classification of methods related to the diagnosis of cognitive disorders. Among them, A.R. Luria's "Memorization of 10 words" test is important. An attempt was made to rely on existing research in testing these methodologies.

Analyze the forms of the obtained graphs, including oral report materials and monitoring of the progress of the work. According to the shape of the curve, it is possible to draw conclusions about the characteristics of memorization. Thus, in healthy subjects, the number of correctly named words increases with each trial. Test-takers with memory impairments tend to increase the number of words less frequently during series and to repeat "extra" words. A large number of "extra" words indicate a disorder of consciousness. When adults are tested for the third repetition, test takers with normal memory typically repeat 9 or 10 words correctly. A memorization curve may indicate poor concentration or severe fatigue. If the subject (adult or child) immediately repeats 8-9 words, and then each time less and less (the curve in the graph does not increase, but decreases), it represents a symptom of increasing fatigue. Also, if the test taker

repeats fewer and fewer words, this may indicate forgetfulness and poor attention span. The zigzag nature of the curve indicates instability of focus. The research was carried out on patients with brain organic disorder, neurosis, postpartum stress, brain injury, and stroke. Also, an event of expert evaluation of this methodology was carried out by experts.

Analysis of the research problem. Relying on the procedure of the test and the existing research experiences in this regard, we selected the following words as stimulus materials in our research and found it necessary to conduct the experiment in 5 series based on the nature of the research object and the methodology.

In the test, the stimuli were words, and the test series took the form of the following statement:

Words	Series				
	1	2	3	4	5
1. Chalk					
2. Word					
3. Horse					
4. Closet					
5. Sound					
6. Chair					
7. Mouth					
8. Linen					
9. Nina					
10. Shade					

In the initial state of the results of the experiment, the indicators for the types of diseases and test series were taken into account.

1-table

Indicators of patients with impaired cognitive functions according to the "Memorization of 10 words" method

Illnesses	Age	Tests					Score
		1-Series	2-Series	3-Series	4-Series	5-Series	
Atherosclerosis	51,36	4,11	3,66	3,77	3,66	2,77	2

Stroke	43,12	3,85	4	4,71	3,85	3,28	2
Postpartum stress	28,71	4,75	5,37	5	4,37	4,62	3
Traumatic brain injury	37,47	4,5	4,33	4,83	4,5	3,5	2
Neurosis	48,21	4,7	4,9	5,4	5	4,7	3

There is a slight decrease in the indicators of the examinees on the types of diseases in the 1st series and in the 5th series in the order of word recall. According to the characteristics obtained in the research, the characteristic of immediate recall is changing. The genesis of asthenia in this category of patients may also occur under the influence of psychogenic and postinfectious factors. Their memory impairment is usually limited to the use of inappropriate words and deficits. This causes a decrease in memory recovery. Sufficient recall is detected even before significant memory impairments. Thus, a patient who repeats 5 words after 10-4 repetitions, after a break of 15-20 minutes, reaches the level where he can remember only a part of these words. A gradual decline in recall is accompanied by a decline in recall. Impairment of memory in patients with cerebral atherosclerosis due to memory impairment coincides with the degree of cognitive impairment. In patients with cerebral atherosclerosis, the performance of the "recall 10 words" test is observed unevenly and with a decrease in the "recall curve" (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Diagram of performance of patients with cerebrovascular diseases on the test "Memorization of 10 words"

This trend was not observed in patients with stroke either in series 1 (3.85) or in series 5 (3.28). Memory impairment due to stroke is also common in daily observations. A part of the brain cannot perform its task due to a violation of blood circulation in the brain. Depending on the localization of the problem, disorders may concern motor functions and coordination, kinesthetic sensitivity, sensory organs, functions, attention and memory. Often, disorders do not affect

one area, but several functions at the same time. In most cases, memory impairment is noted due to stroke. The reason for this is that the memory does not have a specific localization. It has an activity related to the whole surface of the brain. In our research, we should not forget that it is the basis of attention to the application of diagnostic tools, not to stop at all cognitive disorders caused by stroke.

We can conclude that the application of A.R. Luria's test is also useful in the diagnosis of memory characteristics of patients with stroke, like the above patients. Empirically, it was observed that the results of the tests applied to them, like other patients, appeared uneven (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Chart of stroke patients' performance on the "10-word memorization" test

Memory impairments also lead to regression, not progression, of word recall in the final series in stroke patients. It can be concluded that the memory impairment in nonverbal stroke patients also has an impact on the impairment of thinking.

Uneven changes were observed in the test series in memory characteristics of patients with brain injury. Memory disorders caused by traumatic brain injury vary according to the nature of the neurotrauma. Fig. 3 shows that even in this category of patients, the recall may be uneven.

Figure 3. Diagram of brain injury patients' performance on the “10-word memorization” test

In the study, it was found that the changes in memory are significantly different from those of the above patients, because the causes of the disease of the two categories of patients depend more on the social environment and personality characteristics, as well as psychological characteristics. However, it was also observed in empirical indicators that the test of "remembering 10 words" can be used in the diagnosis of a condition specific to the memory of this category of patients (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Patients experiencing post-operative stress, chart of scores on the “10-word memorization” test

Postpartum stress has a unique effect on the psyche of the mother. Such stresses can cause disruption of somatic and mental functions in mothers. Somatic damage causes mental changes, i.e. hypochondria, asthenia, insomnia and weight loss¹. Even the consequences of changes in the mother's experiences and memory characteristics can have negative consequences for the development of the unborn child. Children of mothers who experience postpartum stress lag behind in psychomotor development, experience problems with memory and

¹. Goodman Janice H. Paternal postpartum depression, its relationship to maternal postpartum depression, and implications for family health // Journal of Advanced Nursing. 2004. Vol.45. №1. P. 26–35.

concentration². A high level of distraction³, a decrease in intelligence⁴, in the future they will have a bad mastery of the educational process⁵, and according to R. Galler Janina and his followers, they will have difficulties even in obtaining higher education⁶.

For this reason, disorders in the cognitive functions of postpartum mothers, in particular, memory diagnosis, are among the specific problems of the medical psychodiagnostics system. In the study, it was observed that the immediate recall characteristics of this category of patients when experiencing postpartum stress are not normal (Figure 4). They suggest that the processes of recall and recall, and recall when necessary, can be normalized at the expense of stress relief.

Although the application of the "Memorization of 10 words" test in the diagnosis of memory of patients with neurosis also reflects the relative priority of memory characteristics in empirical indicators compared to patients with atherosclerosis, cerebrovascular diseases, brain injury (table and Figure 5), but in them also has its own problems with memory. One of the most characteristic features of the memory of patients with neurosis are complaints about memory loss. The results of memory tasks for patients with neurosis, their achievements and errors cannot be estimated in advance. They often make mistakes on simple, elementary actions and instead perform more difficult series; they often repeat more, and sometimes more, numbers in reverse order than the correct number. There is no doubt that sometimes their excessive self-criticism leads to the limitation of activity.

² Новорожденные высокого риска / под ред. В.И.Кулакова, Ю.И.Барашнева. М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2006. 528 с.; Fowles ER, Murphey C. Nutrition and mental health in early pregnancy: a pilot study. J Midwifery Womens Health. 2009 JanFeb; 54 (1): 73–7.; 1

³ Janet A. DiPietro. The Role of Prenatal Maternal Stress in Child Development // Current Directions in Psychological Science. 2004. Vol.13., №2. P.71 ;

⁴ Irene van Bokhoven, Walter Matthys, Stephanie van Goozen, Herman van Engeland. Prediction of treatment outcome in children with disruptive behaviour disorders: A study of neurobiological, neuropsychological and psychosocial factors; Prevention and treatment of conduct disorders // 16th World Congress of the International Association for Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Allied Professions (IACAPAP) Berlin / Germany, 2004.; 21. Nissen E, Jonas K, Johansson LM, Ejdebьдск M, RansjьArvidson AB, Увндь-Moberg K. Effects of intrapartum oxytocin administration and epidural analgesia on the concentration of plasma oxytocin and prolactin, in response to suckling during the second day postpartum. Breastfeed Med. 2009 Jun;4(2):71–82.

⁵ Fowles ER, Murphey C. Nutrition and mental health in early pregnancy: a pilot study. J Midwifery Womens Health. 2009 JanFeb; 54 (1): 73–7.

⁶ Galler Janina R., Ramsey Frank C., Harrison Robert H. et al. Postpartum maternal moods and infant size predict performance on a national high school entrance examination // Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry, Volume 45, Issue 6, Page 1064–1075, Sep 2004.

Figure 5. Diagram of scores of patients with neurosis on the "10-word memorization" test

The curves of recall of a series of words of neurotic patients differ significantly from those of the above patients. In turn, their memory is unstable: the patient "forgets" what he said; it was observed that many patients repeat the same word several times without correcting the error in most scores. As one of the features of word reproduction by patients experiencing neurosis, they noted the severity of the "edge effect" - during the study, it was observed that almost all patients remembered and recalled the first words of the series more (Fig. 5).

In our second line of research on the diagnosis of cognitive function disorders, the "Memorization of 10 words" test, together with the "Memory of 10 words" test, the "Express-methodology of the assessment of the mnemonic-intellectual field in old age", the "Recall numbers" test, " Empirical experiments can be carried out on the "Visual memory" test and Benton's "Visual retention" tests in the same order, and it is appropriate to include them in the system of tools used for medical and psychological diagnostic purposes.

As described above, the use characteristics of the "Memorizing 10 words" test for medical psychodiagnostics purposes were asked to rate the level of use by the experts in the field (Table 2).

2- Table

Indicators of experts on the scale of assessment of the level of use of psychodiagnostic methodology for medical diagnosis ("10 words memorization" test) (N=31)

N ^o	Criteria	X	σ
	Implementation time indicator of the methodology	4,54	0,62
	Convenience of specialists to work on the methodology	4,38	0,71

Ease of implementation of the methodology by the examiner	4,22	0,61
The possibility of using the methodology in medical diagnostics	4,23	0,67
The importance of using methodology in medical research	4,52	0,62
Utilization indicator	4,38	0,65

Conclusions. The experts evaluated the timeliness of the "Memorization of 10 words" test for use in medical diagnostic practice (4.54 points). The methodology is convenient for practical use in terms of time. According to the second assessment criterion, it is necessary to provide specific instructions for specialists to work on the methodology (4.38 points).

During the evaluation process (4,22), some comments were made by experts that some difficulties were observed during the application of the test to the patients. Some patients do not need to experience mental stress during the test series.

However, experts have recognized that the use of the test in medical research is useful for determining specific measures for cognitive function disorders, in particular, memory-related treatment measures and disease characteristics (4.52 points).

The average score of experts on the practical use of the methodology was 4.38 points. This gives the conclusion that the characteristics of the method's application for diagnostic purposes are 90% important in the 5-point system.

As a clear example of methods for assessing the specificity of memory processes, the "Memorization of 10 words" test was evaluated as the simplicity of the stimulus materials, the convenience of the time standard for conducting the test, the possibility of making an individual diagnosis, and the methodology with a clear standard.

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